

INFLUENCE OF WATER ABSORPTION ON LONG-TERM STRENGTHS IN VARIOUS DIRECTIONS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP FOR MARINE USE

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ABSTRACT

We have proposed a general and rigorous accelerated testing methodology (ATM) which can be applied to the life prediction of CFRP exposed to an actual load and environment histories. The most important condition for ATM is the fact that the time and temperature dependence on the strength of CFRP is controlled by the viscoelasticity of matrix resin. The objective of this paper is to clear the influence of water absorption on the long-term strengths in various directions of unidirectional CFRP for marine use which consists of vinylester resin as a matrix. First, the master curves for the viscoelasticity of matrix vinylester resin in the wide range of time at a reference temperature under dry and wet conditions are determined using the viscoelasticity measured in the short range of time at various temperatures under dry and wet conditions based on the time-temperature superposition principle. Second, the tensile and compressive static strengths in the longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CFRP are measured at various temperatures under dry and wet conditions. Third, the long-term static strengths in various directions of unidirectional CFRP under dry and wet conditions are predicted by applying the same time-temperature superposition principle as that for the matrix resin to the measured strengths. Finally, the influence of water absorption on the long-term static strengths in various directions of unidirectional CFRP is cleared and the applicability of ATM for these strengths is also discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are now being used for the primary structures of airplanes, ships and others, in which the high reliability should be kept during the long-term operation. Therefore, it would be expected that the accelerated testing methodology for the long-term life prediction of CFRP structures exposed under the actual environments of temperature, water, and others must be established.

We have proposed a general and rigorous advanced accelerated testing methodology (ATM) which can be applied to the life prediction of CFRP exposed to an actual load and environment history based on the three conditions [1]. The most important condition is the fact that the time and temperature dependence on the strength of CFRP is controlled by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin. The formulations of creep compliance and time-temperature shift factors of matrix resin are carried out based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). The formulations of long-term life of CFRP under an actual loading are carried out based on the three conditions.

In this paper, the tensile and compressive static strengths in the longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CFRP under dry and wet conditions are evaluated using ATM. The applicability of ATM and the effect of water absorption on time and temperature dependence of these static strengths are discussed.

2 ATM

ATM is established with following three conditions: (A) the failure probability is independent of time, temperature and load history; (B) the time and temperature dependence of strength of CFRP is controlled by the viscoelasticity of matrix resin. Therefore, the TTSP for the viscoelasticity of matrix resin holds for the strength of CFRP; (C) the strength degradation of CFRP holds the linear cumulative damage law as the cumulative damage under cyclic loading [2].

The master curve of static strength can be shown by the following equation based on ATM.

$$\log \sigma_f(t', T_0, P_f) = \log \sigma_{f0}(t_0', T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - n_r \log \left[\frac{D^*(t', T_0)}{D_c(t_0', T_0)} \right] \quad (1)$$

The first term of right part shows the reference strength (scale parameter for the static strength) at reduced reference time t_0' under the reference temperature T_0 . The second term shows the scatter of static strength as the function of failure probability P_f based on condition (A). α is the shape parameter for the strength. The third term shows the variation by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin which depend on temperature and load histories. n_r is the material parameter which is determined by the failure mode. The viscoelastic compliance D^* in (1) can be shown by the following equation,

$$D^*(t', T_0) = \frac{\varepsilon(t', T_0)}{\sigma(t', T_0)} = \frac{\int_0^{t'} D_c(t' - \tau', T_0) \frac{d\sigma(\tau')}{d\tau'} d\tau'}{\sigma(t', T_0)}, \quad t' = \int_0^{t'} \frac{d\tau}{a_{\tau_0}(T(\tau))} \quad (2)$$

where D_c shows the creep compliance of matrix resin and $\sigma(\tau')$ shows the stress history. t' is the reduced time at T_0 , a_{τ_0} shows the time-temperature shift factor of matrix resin and $T(\tau)$ shows the temperature history. The viscoelastic compliance D^* under constant deformation rate loading (static loading) can be shown by

$$D^*(t', T_0) \cong D_c(t'/2, T_0) \quad (3)$$

Condition (C) is not considered here because the static loading employed in the tests is monotonic.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Unidirectional CFRP laminates T700/Derakane which consists of carbon fiber T700 unidirectional non-crimp fabric (Toray) and vinylester resin Derakane 411-350 (Ashland) were employed in this study. The laminates were molded by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding technique and then cured at room temperature for 24hours. The post-cure is conducted at 150°C for 2hours. The Wet specimens by soaking the aged specimen (Dry specimen) in hot water of 95°C for 25hours for 1mm thick specimen, 95°C for 50hours for 2mm thick specimens were respectively prepared. The water content of wet specimens was 0.7 wt%.

The dynamic viscoelastic tests for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP were carried out at various frequencies and temperatures to construct the master curve of creep compliance for matrix resin. The static tests for typical four directions of unidirectional CFRP were carried out at various temperatures to construct the master curves of static strength for unidirectional CFRP. Longitudinal tension tests were carried out according with SACMA 4R-94 using 1mm thick specimens. Longitudinal bending tests were carried out according with ISO 14125 to get the longitudinal compressive static strengths using 2mm specimens. Transverse bending tests were carried out according with ISO 14125 to get the transverse tensile static strengths using 2mm specimens. Transverse compression tests were carried out according with SACMA 1R-94 using 2mm specimens .

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Viscoelastic behaviour of matrix resin

The left side of Figure 1 shows the loss tangent $\tan \delta$ for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP (Dry specimen) versus time t , where t is the inverse of frequency. The right side shows the master curve of $\tan \delta$ which is constructed by shifting $\tan \delta$ at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since $\tan \delta$ at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for $\tan \delta$ for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP. The master curve of $\tan \delta$ for Wet specimens can be also constructed as shown in Figure 1. The TTSP is also applicable for $\tan \delta$ under wet condition. The master curve of $\tan \delta$ is shifted to the left side by water absorption as shown in Figure 1.

The left side of Figure 2 shows the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP (Dry specimen) versus time t . The right side shows the master curve of E' which is constructed by shifting horizontally and vertically E' at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t using the same shift amount for $\tan \delta$ and along the logarithmic scale of E' until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since E' at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP. The master curve of E' for Wet specimens can be also constructed as shown in Figure 2. The TTSP is also applicable for E' under wet condition.

The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ which is the horizontal shift amount shown in the left portion of Figure 3 can be formulated by the following equation:

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) + \left[\frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T_g} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) + \frac{\Delta H_2}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (4)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K·mol)], ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 are the activation energies below and above the glass transition temperature T_g , respectively. H is the Heaviside step function.

The temperature shift factor $b_{T_0}(T)$ which is the amount of vertical shift shown in the right portion of Figure 3 can be fit with the following equation:

$$\log b_{T_0}(T) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^5 b_{i-1} (T - T_0)^{i-1} \right] H(T_g - T) + \left[\sum_{i=1}^5 b_{i-1} (T_g - T_0)^{i-1} + \log \frac{T_g}{T} \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (5)$$

where b_i are the fitting parameters.

The storage modulus E' of matrix resin is back-calculated from the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP using the approximate averaging method by Uemura [3]. And the creep compliance D_c of matrix resin is obtained from the storage modulus of matrix resin by the following equation [4].

$$D_c(t) \sim 1/E(t), \quad E(t) \cong E'(\omega) \Big|_{\omega \rightarrow 2/\pi} \quad (6)$$

The master curves of back-calculated D_c of matrix resin are shown in Figure 4. The master curve of D_c can be formulated by the following equation:

$$\log D_c = \log D_{c,0}(t'_0, T_0) + \log \left[\left(\frac{t'}{t'_0} \right)^{m_g} + \left(\frac{t'}{t'_g} \right)^{m_r} \right] \quad (7)$$

where $D_{c,0}$ is the creep compliance at reduced reference time t'_0 and reference temperature T_0 , and t'_g is the glassy reduced time on T_0 , and m_g and m_r are the gradients in glassy and rubbery regions of D_c master curve.

Figure 1: Master curves of loss tangent for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Figure 2: Master curves of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Figure 3: Shift factors of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Figure 4: Master curves of creep compliance for matrix resin calculated from the storage modulus for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

4.2 Master curves of static strengths for unidirectional CFRP

Figures 5 and 6 show the master curves of static strengths for longitudinal tension X , longitudinal compression X' , transverse tension Y and transverse compression Y' for Dry and Wet specimens of unidirectional CFRP obtained from the strength data at various temperatures by using the time-temperature shift factors a_{T_0} shown in Figure 3. The solid and dotted curves in these figures show the fitting curves by Equation (1) using the master curves of creep compliance of matrix resin in Figure 4. From these figures, the static strengths of unidirectional CFRP decrease with increasing time, temperature and water absorption. The time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strength of unidirectional CFRP are different with the loading direction.

The fitting curves of X and X' agree well with the experimental data for both of Dry and Wet specimens, however the fitting curves of Y and Y' do not so agree with the experimental data as shown in Figures 5 and 6. The reason why these two figures show different behavior is discussed in the next section.

4.3 Relationship between static strengths and viscoelasticity of matrix resin

Figures 7 and 8 show the relationship between the static strength of unidirectional CFRP and the viscoelastic compliance of corresponding matrix resin. The slopes of this relation for X and X' in Figure 7 are straight and correspond to the parameter n_r in Equation (1). These slopes of X and X' depend on the loading direction while that changes scarcely with water absorption. It is cleared from these facts that the time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strength of the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP can be uniquely determined by the viscoelastic behavior of corresponding matrix resin. The influence of water absorption for X and X' is appeared to the level of strength and both levels of X and X' decrease with water absorption.

The experimental data of these relations for Y and Y' in Figure 8 do not make straight lines and make modelate curves against the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin. It is cleared from these facts that the time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strength of the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP can be also uniquely determined by the viscoelastic behavior of corresponding matrix resin, however it can be presumed that these dependencies are not directly influenced by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin.

Figure 5: Master curves of tensile and compressive strengths in the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP

Figure 6: Master curves of tensile and compressive strengths in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Figure 7: Relationship between the static strength in the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP and the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin

Figure 8: Relationship between the static strength in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP and the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin

5 CONCLUSIONS

The tensile and compressive static strengths in the longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CFRP under dry and wet conditions were evaluated using the accelerated testing methodology (ATM) proposed in the previous papers by authors. It is cleared that the time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strengths in these various load directions of unidirectional CFRP are uniquely determined by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin.

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